

TOWARDS GLOBAL BIODATA PARTNERSHIPS

*An exploratory study of adoption,
practices, drivers and barriers*

EMBL-EBI

 Research
Consulting

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY (1/2)

The European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) commissioned this exploratory study to assess and optimise engagement with biodata users, contributors and delivery partners across low-resource settings. Through analysis of web analytics data and interviews with 18 researchers across Africa, Asia and Latin America, we examined the technical, cultural and policy factors that shape participation in the global biodata ecosystem. We highlight the following key findings.

Data analytics showcase significant interest and engagement from low-resource settings.

- Low-resource settings generated 5.3 billion total requests from 18.5 million unique IP addresses to EMBL-EBI resources in 2024. At the same time, by 2024, high-income countries generated 4 requests for every 1 request from all other countries combined. The gap between settings may therefore be less about access and more about ensuring that researchers in all regions can derive full value from biodata and bioinformatics resources.
- Only 11% of data deposits to the European Nucleotide Archive, one of the largest biodata resources hosted by EMBL-EBI, originate from low-resource settings. This usage-contribution gap highlights that barriers to participation go beyond economic classifications and points to deeper structural challenges that merit closer examination.

Barriers across infrastructure, research practices and funding landscapes hinder engagement with biodata resources.

- Some countries have developed robust national supercomputing infrastructure, whereas others face fundamental challenges with internet connectivity, data storage and computational resources. It is important to acknowledge this variation in technical resources, embracing the fact that there cannot be a one-size-fits-all approach to improving the current landscape.
- A number of constraints beyond technology limit progress in low-resource settings. For example, there is a persistent shortage of trained bioinformaticians across all regions studied, and "brain drain" of skilled professionals to industry or high-income countries undermines local capacity.
- Researchers increasingly resist models whereby data is extracted from low-resource settings, with a growing emphasis on data sovereignty (e.g. via federated infrastructure) and equitable partnerships. There is also a need for attribution mechanisms that ensure fair recognition.
- Project-based funding dominates, preventing long-term sustainability. This is compounded by changes in political leadership, which disrupt scientific infrastructure investments and the work of researchers in the field. In this context, dependency on international collaborations continues to create power imbalances.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY (2/2)

This study shows that the global biodata divide is not primarily about access to resources, as researchers in low-resource settings are already active users of open biodata infrastructure.

The real challenge lies in creating conditions that enable these researchers to contribute and thrive as equal partners. As a result, success requires moving beyond technical solutions to address the complex interplay of infrastructure, cultural practices and policy environments that shape scientific participation.

Building truly global biodata and bioinformatics partnerships requires approaches that respect local contexts, prioritise community-driven innovation and are centred around the needs of researchers in low-resource settings.

This landscape analysis has identified strategic opportunities where EMBL-EBI can catalyse this transformation while acknowledging its varying degrees of influence across different domains. While EMBL-EBI can directly reshape its technical infrastructure to better serve global users, advancing changes in research practices and policy environments will require leveraging partnerships and deepening engagement with the full spectrum of stakeholders - from individual researchers to delivery partners and funders - across low-resource settings.

Our landscape analysis has identified three practical recommendations to enhance EMBL-EBI's support for biodata and bioinformatics resources in low-resource settings:

1. **EMBL-EBI should establish or strengthen connections with existing national, regional or broader genomics and bioinformatics projects or networks**, avoiding the creation of new structures. These networks possess the local trust, contextual understanding, and operational infrastructure essential for effective engagement.
2. **Through these channels, EMBL-EBI should invest in deeply understanding local needs, priorities and challenges.** This includes identifying opportunities to support local delivery partners in professionalising and maturing their services to participate more effectively in global infrastructure networks through targeted skills cascade approaches.
3. **With trust and understanding established, EMBL-EBI can then co-develop solutions with local stakeholders that address specific regional needs.** This includes not only technical tools adapted for infrastructure constraints, but also culturally-appropriate support systems and strategies to advocate for policy change. By ensuring all interventions are co-created rather than imposed, EMBL-EBI can build the local ownership and capacity necessary for long-term sustainability and a truly equitable global biodata ecosystem.

INTRODUCTION

Global biodata infrastructure encompasses the worldwide network of systems that handle life sciences information throughout its lifecycle, from collection and storage to analysis and sharing.¹ This includes specialised databases, research repositories, analytical tools and communication channels that, together, enable scientists around the world to collaborate on life sciences research.

Inclusive and representative biodata and bioinformatics resources are essential to the achievement of scientific breakthroughs in several disciplines with global relevance, including health, agriculture and biodiversity conservation.² As a result, it is important to encourage broad participation in the creation, maintenance and long-term sustainability of these resources, aiming to achieve a sense of shared responsibility as well as ownership. The ultimate goal is to ensure that the potential benefits arising from the use of biodata and bioinformatics resources are distributed equitably rather than concentrated in wealthier regions or countries.

In this context, the European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI)^a aimed to assess and optimise its engagement efforts with biodata contributors and users as well as organisations maintaining and delivering these. EMBL-EBI is one of the six sites of the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), an intergovernmental research organisation funded by 29 member states, two prospect and one associate member states. EMBL-EBI manages the world's most comprehensive suite of freely available data resources and tools in the life sciences.³

EMBL-EBI commissioned Research Consulting to run a stakeholder consultation that led to the preparation of this report. This initiative is part of the 'Listening & awareness' workstream of a Wellcome-funded project led by EMBL-EBI aiming to explore ways to build life science infrastructures that are truly global. As part of this workstream, EMBL-EBI sought to better understand the local contexts in low-resource settings to inform its own decision making and optimise its data resources and tools for global use.

ABOUT THIS REPORT

As part of this work, we examined analytics provided by EMBL-EBI to explore how, currently, stakeholders from low-resource settings engage with the Institute, its bioinformatics resources and biodata. This data helped frame the findings from a mix of published literature and individual perspectives shared by stakeholders in low-resource settings. Participants in our consultation included individuals from Africa (five interviewees), Asia (seven interviewees) and Latin America (six interviewees). Due to the small sample size, we have not included contributors' names to preserve anonymity.

By using the COM-B model⁴ – a behaviour change framework that assesses capability (C), opportunity (O), and motivation (M) – we assessed ways in which EMBL-EBI can further grow its efforts in support of researchers and partners in low-resource settings. In our analysis, we examined use cases for both contributors to biodata resources and users, as well as their local policy contexts and how these affect the everyday reality of life sciences research (with a focus on omics research).

A key objective of this work was to identify areas where action from EMBL-EBI would be especially impactful and should be prioritised, as opposed to high-level geopolitical challenges where EMBL-EBI's influence would naturally be more limited.

Given the relatively small sample of participants, the narratives presented in this document should be understood as illustrative rather than comprehensive and may not represent all experiences.

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01.

**EMBL-EBI'S GLOBAL
REACH**

AN INTRODUCTION TO EMBL-EBI'S RESOURCES

EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI) maintains the world's most comprehensive range of freely available molecular data resources. This interconnected ecosystem of databases and tools collectively archive, integrate, and analyse diverse biological data-including DNA, proteins, metabolites, structures and pathways, as well as indexing scientific literature-to support global life sciences research.

As a major hub for deposition databases, EMBL-EBI enables researchers worldwide to submit and share their data. Expert curators enhance these submissions through annotation and integration with other sources, increasingly leveraging AI and machine learning tools to scale their efforts, subject to rigorous quality control.

EMBL is dedicated to making science open and accessible to the global scientific community. This commitment, combined with EMBL-EBI's Terms of Use and Licensing terms, means that databases, code and software are freely available to scientists whenever possible, with no additional restrictions on data use beyond those imposed by data owners. About 40 large data resources are available, with some example on this page; a full list of resources and tools can be explored online.

USAGE OF EMBL-EBI'S RESOURCES IN LOW-RESOURCE SETTINGS (1/2)

Prior to our stakeholder consultation, we explored the extent to which EMBL-EBI resources reach and are used across the world.

Using EMBL-EBI's web analytics data, we established that, in 2024 (the latest complete year in the dataset), the Institute's data resources received over 44.9 billion total requests from over 41.5 million unique IP addresses across 100+ countries.

Based on the [OECD's list of recipients of official development assistance](#),⁺ we established that over 5.3 billion of the total requests, from 18.5 million unique IP addresses, can be attributed to low-resource settings, including [least-developed, low-income, lower-middle- and upper-middle-income countries](#)* (Figure 1).

The peaks in 2020 and 2021 are likely to be attributable to increased usage during the COVID-19 pandemic. It may be hypothesised that, in high-income countries, researchers could more easily access online biodata resources when working remotely, which may have caused the higher increase in IP addresses (i.e. as opposed to accessing these from a smaller number of institutional IPs, for example). On the other hand, a combination of lower researcher numbers and limitations in the bandwidth of home connections (or lack of home internet access altogether) across low-resource settings may be responsible for the smaller increases in usage in the same period.

Figure 1. Unique IP addresses visiting EMBL-EBI resources by economic classification

* Referring to specific geographical regions is typically more accurate and inclusive than using broad terms like 'Low- and Middle-Income Country (LMIC)' or 'global south', which categorise countries primarily by economic status and can unintentionally reinforce a sense of 'otherness'. However, in this report, this terminology is used intentionally to draw attention to issues of power and resource disparities - key themes that require transparency and action. In this context, identifying a partner country's income status is relevant. It remains essential, however, to reflect carefully before applying such labels, ensuring they are appropriate to the context and that the intended message is clearly communicated to the audience.

USAGE OF EMBL-EBI'S RESOURCES IN LOW-RESOURCE SETTINGS (2/2)

While the number of unique IP addresses visiting EMBL-EBI resources is fairly stable across years 2019-2024 in each setting (with the exception of 2021, see Figure 1), the total number of requests to EMBL-EBI has been accelerating in high-income countries (Figure 2).

It is especially striking to notice that the gap between requests from high income countries and all other countries summed together has tripled over the 5-year period shown:

- Gap in 2019: 5.2 billion requests
- Gap in 2024: 15.6 billion requests

In practice, by 2024, high-income countries generated 4 requests for every 1 request from all other countries combined, perhaps reflecting emerging patterns of data-intensive usage in these settings (e.g. training AI models).

This suggests that the gap between settings may be less about access - as many researchers in low resource settings are already active users of biodata infrastructure - and more about ensuring that researchers in all regions can derive full value from data resources.

Figure 2. Total requests to EMBL-EBI resources by economic classification

EXAMINING DATA DEPOSIT TRENDS

Using the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) as an example, as one of the largest biodata resources hosted by EMBL-EBI, we explored data deposit trends. This assessment sought to identify differences in deposit numbers based on the economic classification of countries, as an input into our stakeholder consultation.

Figure 3 shows that a majority of data deposits to ENA in 2024, which totalled over 811,000, came from high-income countries (63%), followed by upper-middle-income countries (26%). This indicates that considering all low- and middle-income countries together (which are commonly referred to using the LMIC acronym) can be misleading in this case, as a stark difference exists between upper-middle- and lower-middle-income countries.

Additionally, these figures led us to investigating data sharing opportunities, attitudes and skills as part of our literature review and stakeholder interviews, as discussed in the next section. This effort sought to investigate if lower submission rates may be due to technical reasons, customs, funding or other considerations.

Figure 3. Percentage of submitted sequences to the European Nucleotide Archive (2024) by economic classification

EXPLORING ENGAGEMENT PATTERNS WITH EMBL-EBI RESOURCES

To further explore international variation, we examined data on online on-demand training attendance (typically occurring prior to resource usage) and mentions of EMBL-EBI resources in published articles (typically occurring after resource usage). When these statistics are presented together and sorted, some trends become apparent (Figure 4). The decreasing share for middle-income countries across these modes of engagement is especially interesting and suggests that countries within this economic classification may face cumulative barriers as scientific activities become more resource-intensive. The data shown indicates that barriers may increase when generating and submitting original research data (more infrastructure and equipment as well as participants are needed); participating in capacity-building opportunities (high language proficiency, time, stable internet connection are needed); and publishing in open access journals (funds to cover article processing charges are needed).

These patterns shows that true scientific equity requires addressing the entire ecosystem, not just individual barriers, to ensure that researchers and organisations in low-resource settings can derive full value from biodata and bioinformatics resources.

Figure 4. Engagement with EMBL-EBI resources and online on-demand training by economic classification (2024 data)

* Mentions were calculated based on open access articles available via Europe PMC. † Lower-middle- and upper-middle-income countries have been combined in this visual to showcase high-level trends.

DATA ANALYTICS HIGHLIGHT KEY PRIORITIES FOR VALIDATION WITH THE COMMUNITY

Our analysis showcases a complex divide that goes beyond access barriers. The data tells a story of active engagement coupled with systemic contribution challenges across low-resource settings.

Substantial but unequal usage: EMBL-EBI resources received 44.9 billion hits globally in 2024, of which 5.3 billion were from low-resource settings. The most notable challenge to tackle is not about access: it lies in creating conditions that enable researchers and organisations in low-resource settings to contribute and thrive as equal partners.

The participation paradox: Despite 18.5 million unique IP addresses from low-resource settings accessing EMBL-EBI resources (representing 45% of all visits from unique IP addresses), upper-middle-income countries account for 26% of deposits, while lower-middle-income and least developed countries contribute just 8% and 3% respectively.

Cascading barriers across the research lifecycle: Our data reveals a shrinking pattern in participation. As scientific activities become more resource-intensive, participation from middle-income countries progressively decreases across resource access, data generation and submission, training participation and citation of EMBL-EBI's data resources in publications.

This usage-contribution gap demands investigation beyond statistics. While researchers in low-resource settings actively seek biodata resources, barriers appear to be preventing them from becoming full participants in the global biodata ecosystem. Understanding these barriers requires examining the intersection of infrastructure limitations, institutional capacity funding mechanisms and policy frameworks that shape daily research realities across different countries.

The following section explores these topics through engagement with researchers across Africa, Asia and Latin America.

02.

**FINDINGS AND KEY
PERSPECTIVES**

THE ELEMENTS FOR SUCCESSFUL BIODATA AND BIOINFORMATICS RESOURCES

Creating globally equitable biodata and bioinformatics resources depends on a range of factors including robust technical infrastructure, supportive research norms and practices, and enabling policy frameworks.

- 1 Technical infrastructure is the underlying and essential dimension that enables equitable bioinformatics resources. In other words, it provides the physical and digital backbone that enables researchers to handle the exceptional volume of data characteristic of modern life sciences.⁵

From high-speed connectivity and adequate storage capacity to sustainable computing resources and reliable power supplies, these technical elements determine whether researchers can effectively access, generate, analyse and share data, particularly when working with datasets that routinely reach terabyte scale.⁶

- 2 Research norms and practices represent the human dimension of biodata resources, where a set of key skills and capabilities are essential for making biodata available for access and effectively reusing it.⁷

Human capacity can be built through training pathways that help develop specialised expertise, awareness raising efforts, clear data governance frameworks that address ethical concerns, standardised approaches to data management and sustainable career pathways that retain skilled professionals.⁸ Without these elements, even the most advanced infrastructure remains underutilised or inaccessible.

- 3 The third dimension is the funding and policy landscape that determines whether and how easily biodata and bioinformatics resources can be maintained and developed over time. Sustainable funding mechanisms that transcend short-term project cycles and supportive national policies for research shape the longevity and inclusivity of biodata and bioinformatics resources.⁹

The following pages explore each of these critical dimensions in more detail, examining how they manifest across different geographical contexts and research environments through a collection of quotes from our stakeholder interviews and illustrative case studies.

Dimension 1

TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Technical infrastructure is the basic requirement for the delivery of a global biodata and bioinformatics ecosystem. Like physical roads and bridges enable the movement of people and goods, digital infrastructure enables the movement of scientific data, determining who can participate in the global exchange of biodata and how effectively they can do so.

The need for robust digital infrastructures is particularly acute in biodata research due to the unprecedented scale of modern biological datasets: gigabyte- and terabyte-scale datasets create technical demands that amplify existing infrastructure disparities and can significantly hinder engagement with, deposit and reuse of existing resources.

Connectivity challenges prevent engagement in low-resource settings

Despite evidence of global engagement with biodata resources by stakeholders in low-resource settings, our consultation highlighted considerable variation in experiences. While some researchers reported relatively stable access to biodata and bioinformatics resources, others described significant barriers that apply in particular to the use of large datasets or engagement with cloud-based solutions; this might be tied to the patterns identified in web analytics (see section 1), where total hits from high-income countries are growing significantly more quickly compared to low-resource settings. As one researcher in an Asian country noted, unreliable connectivity regularly disrupts operations: "The only limitation at times is Internet access speed... sometimes we get disconnected, or even if you are connected, sometimes the speeds are not as fast as they should be." Similarly, a Colombian researcher reported that "just sending data is still as complex as it was 30 years ago, and today the data we are sending is enormous". In this context, the researcher remarked that sometimes data is sent on a disk via mail, which not only slows down research but might also give rise to data protection concerns.

Dimension 1 (continued)

TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Data storage is often limited due to the growth of data-intensive research

The growth in data-intensive methods in the life sciences has created storage demands that outpace institutional capacity, and interviewees highlighted a lack of adequate on-site storage capacity for genomic datasets.¹⁰ A researcher from Uruguay remarked that “We work with human genome data, single cell data or things that are very heavy, so we really quickly run out of capacity.” This can force researchers to make decisions about which data to keep or discard, and limits options for data transfer. The interviewee continued by sharing that “Every so many years we have to go and negotiate with management, looking for funds to obtain storage.” Even well-resourced facilities face these pressures, as noted by a researcher from South Africa: “There’s been a lot of work done over the last decade to increase capacity for bioinformatics and bioinformatics infrastructure... but our other collaborators in other African countries often don’t have access to that kind of infrastructure.” This view was complemented by an interviewee from Tanzania, who highlighted how limited storage impact data backups.

High-performance computing (HPC) capacity is developing asymmetrically

Access to HPC facilities varies substantially across low-resource settings, with a mix of institutional- or national-level provision.¹¹ Based on our consultations, national-level supercomputing infrastructure with substantial computing power and formalised access mechanisms emerged within a few countries. In other countries, more moderate capabilities for high-performance computing are delivered through institutional facilities or local centres. A range of examples that we encountered as part of this research are presented in Case studies 1-4. The ability to deploy national-level facilities is sometimes tied to political instability and changes in government priorities across administrations, as reported by an Argentinian researcher: “The supercluster has not been able to finish being installed, and the decision was entirely political.” In cases where the establishment of large-scale infrastructures is not possible, which may also be due to their significant cost, institutions may rely on smaller computing clusters or project-specific resources. These are easier to secure and deploy, but suffer from long-term sustainability challenges.

THE DEVELOPING GLOBAL LANDSCAPE OF SCIENTIFIC COMPUTING INFRASTRUCTURES

Case Study 1: Indian Biological Data Centre (IBDC)

The IBDC showcases how national investment can create sustainable biodata infrastructure. Established under India's Department of Biotechnology, the IBDC benefits from consistent government funding. The IBDC is integrated with India's National Supercomputing Mission, providing researchers nationwide with merit-based access to advanced computing resources. This democratises access to essential infrastructure that would otherwise be available only to well-funded institutions. India's Biotechnology Information Systems Network (BTISnet), connects over 400 scientists and also support this mission.

Case Study 2: National Laboratory for High Performance Computing

Chile's National Laboratory for High Performance Computing (NLHPC) represents a successful national-level investment in shared computational infrastructure. Hosted at the University of Chile but jointly owned by several universities, it provides free scientific computing services to researchers throughout the country. Initially funded through the National Research Agency's equipment grants and subsequently renewed, NLHPC hosts what is reportedly Latin America's largest computing infrastructure. Researchers apply for computing time through competitive project proposals.

Case Study 3: Brazilian National Biosciences Laboratory (LNBio)

The Brazilian Biosciences National Laboratory (LNBio) focuses on the study of human health, combining integrative biology with advanced technologies. With competencies in gene editing, microphysiological systems, bioimaging and tissue engineering, LNBio aims to discover molecular targets and develop innovative therapies for various illnesses that are of public importance. LNBio houses a cutting-edge Computational Biology Laboratory (LBC) focusing on developing and applying computational tools to solve complex biological problems, in the areas of structural biology, omics, and artificial intelligence in biology.

Case Study 4: Computing services at the Philippine Genome Center

The Philippine Genome Centre (PGC) serves as a central national resource for genomics and bioinformatics across fields including human health, agriculture and biodiversity research. The PGC is significantly expanding its computing capacity by establishing a dedicated data center as part of the Philippine Genomics Information and Resource Hub (Philomics) initiative. The PGC model extends beyond centralised services through satellite centres strategically placed throughout the archipelago, allowing researchers across the country to access bioinformatics resources. Regional centres balance mirroring core capabilities with specialised focus areas aligned with local priorities.

Stories from the community

"Until a few years ago, access to high-performance computing was restricted to whoever had the money to buy facilities of that kind. About five years ago, things changed through the National Supercomputing Mission. Under this, several supercomputers were commissioned across the country. Now, people can write a grant and, upon review, be given time on these."

By March 2025, the Indian National Supercomputing Mission (NSM) had deployed 34 supercomputers with 35 Petaflops of combined capacity. The network supports over 10,000 researchers and 1,700 PhD scholars advancing critical areas like drug discovery, climate science, energy security and astrophysics. Many supercomputers operate at over 95% capacity, demonstrating significant need for computational resources across India's scientific community. Additionally, Over 22,000 individuals were trained in high-performance computing and AI, ensuring India's research community can effectively leverage advanced computational resources.

Dimension 2

NORMS AND CUSTOMS

Beyond technical infrastructure, the invisible architecture of norms, practices and shared understandings determines whether and how researchers engage with biodata and bioinformatics resources. These disciplinary expectations establish what constitutes acceptable research conduct, data management practices and collaborative approaches, creating powerful incentives that guide individual and institutional behaviours.¹²

In low-resource settings, researchers have to navigate both global scientific norms and local realities, often reconciling international expectations with constrained capabilities. Understanding these dynamics is key for developing biodata resources that respect both scientific rigour and the diverse circumstances in which research takes place.

Resource constraints limit workforce capacity in bioinformatics

Developing and retaining skilled bioinformatics professionals remains a critical challenge in low-resource settings.¹³ Although local and online training programmes are available (including from [EMBL-EBI](#) and [Wellcome](#)), participants noted difficulties in finding skilled professionals who can effectively use advanced bioinformatics infrastructure: “Facilities are there, but the trained staff who can use these facilities, they are not there. They are very few. It's very difficult to get trained people who can help you in your projects on bioinformatics and use these facilities effectively.”

Beyond initial staffing challenges, talent migration is also seen as trained bioinformaticians leave local institutions for better-compensated positions in industry or better-resourced organisations abroad.¹⁴ Researchers in South Africa and Argentina emphasised that bioinformaticians, once trained, frequently leave local institutions for better-paying positions in industry or organisations with higher resources in other countries. A South African researcher clearly articulated this challenge: “I'd say the biggest rate limiter for bioinformatics is having money to pay for people. I've got enough people who want to do the work. I don't have the money to employ them.”

Dimension 2 (continued)

NORMS AND CUSTOMS

Researchers struggle to embrace global data practices and customs

Interviews highlighted significant challenges in integrating global data standards into local research workflows. For example, researchers and healthcare professionals in low-resource settings can lack familiarity with standardised data management practices, limiting their ability to effectively share their data and use existing bioinformatics resources.¹⁵ As a participant from the Philippines explained: "I'm a clinical geneticist, so the language of bioinformatics is way over my head... we all need to be on the same page in understanding what those FASTQ files are and what the annotation is." This knowledge gap extends to understanding data standardisation and access protocols.¹⁶ Many researchers described significant challenges in this regard and, in Argentina, researchers noted that the lack of standardised practices makes it difficult to incorporate their data into existing databases. Additionally, researchers expressed uncertainty about how to meet funder expectations regarding data sharing, with limited guidance available on best-practice policies (and their implementation) and standard operating procedures.¹⁷

Concerns about data ownership are limiting willingness to share

According to interviewees, there is apprehension about data sharing, particularly regarding ownership, attribution and potential misuse.¹⁸ Researchers from Tanzania and South Africa specifically highlighted fears that sharing data might lead to others publishing findings before the original data generators could. As a Tanzanian researcher expressed: "Data generators, especially in Africa... some people don't share the data because they are afraid that other scientists will steal the data and their efforts." As a result, there is increasing push-back against traditional data sharing approaches: researchers are advocating for more equitable alternatives, including solutions that keep sensitive data within national boundaries while sharing only results and data sharing agreements that protect local interests and ensure equitable distribution of research benefits.¹⁹ One participant from South Africa noted: "The world of data sharing is changing... We got stuck in a paradigm where sharing means Africans just give their data to global North partners. But there's nothing that says that's the only way to share at all."

Stories from the community

“The facilities are there, but the trained staff who can effectively use these facilities are very few. It's challenging to find skilled personnel who can support bioinformatics projects, as this requires basic knowledge of high-performance computing, programming languages like Python and Perl, and database management. Such specialized training is lacking, and the most talented students, once trained, often leave for opportunities abroad.”

This quote highlights how economic pressures can drive talent away from scientific careers, leading to difficulties in building sustainable bioinformatics capacity. As pursuing a scientific career becomes increasingly precarious for young professionals, a persistent brain drain develops where highly trained researchers either leave academia for industry positions with better compensation or depart for opportunities in countries with higher resources.²⁰ Importantly, technical support staff such as developers specialised in biodata resources are affected by the same considerations, making capacity building an even greater challenge.

Dimension 3

POLICIES AND FUNDING

The sustainability of biodata resources depends on supportive funding mechanisms and policy environments.²¹ While technical infrastructure and research practices form the operational foundation, long-term funding commitments and stable policy frameworks determine whether these resources can be maintained and developed over time.

The interviews describe a complex interplay between shifting political priorities, severe economic constraints and ambitious scientific goals in low-resource settings. The challenge of sustainability also extends to the ongoing costs of maintaining equipment and leveraging it after grant timeframes. Understanding these dynamics is essential for building partnerships that can withstand political transitions and continue to advance capabilities in underrepresented regions.

National funding for biodata research and infrastructure varies significantly

The funding landscape across low-resource settings is extremely varied, which leads to disparities in how researchers and infrastructures can be developed in these regions. In India, government agencies have established institutional funding mechanisms through the Department of Biotechnology to enable robust bioinformatics infrastructure development. [India's National Supercomputing Mission](#) also supports access to high-performance computing to support researchers. By contrast, in many Latin American and African countries, national support for science infrastructure fluctuates with political changes.²²

These variations are compounded by the increasing emphasis from major funders on open data sharing requirements, which can create additional compliance challenges for resource-constrained institutions. As one researcher noted: "The problem is that, when the authorities change, requirements can change completely. This generates a loss of resources and time and inefficiency and setbacks that are sometimes difficult to overcome." The uneven foundation for biodata and bioinformatics research was further illustrated by a Tanzanian researcher: "For research we are not supported by the government... we depend 100% on donor [funding]."

Dimension 3 (continued)

POLICIES AND FUNDING

Funding tends to be project-based, undermining long-term sustainability

Across interviews, researchers consistently highlighted that the funding mechanisms available to them are predominantly in the form of short-term, project-based models with specific timeframes and deliverables. While this approach supports initial development and operations during a given project's timeframe, there is seldom a mechanism to maintain these resources or infrastructures acquired or developed during the project once the funding expires.²³ These funding mechanisms create a cycle where institutions must either divert limited core resources to maintain systems after project funding expires or allow valuable infrastructure to deteriorate, significantly impacting long-term research capabilities as well as leading to underutilisation of equipment or resources that could have had a longer-term impact. Another strategy to maximise the value of funding in cases where new equipment is purchased was shared by a researcher from the Philippines: "When we want to develop something, we look for two or three projects, so that the equipment can be shared across them."

Resource disparities push scientists into collaborations that may be inequitable or serve external interests

The inconsistency of local research funding mechanisms pushes scientists to seek opportunities in environments with more stable support. Some contributors highlighted international collaborations as being essential for accessing both expertise and sustainable resources.²⁴ As an Argentinian researcher described: "I recently had a couple of publications with some groups in Denmark. For those projects, I ended up using the Danish infrastructure... Because locally it was more complicated for me to organise the bioinformatics infrastructure for such a big project." While these collaborations can provide access to advanced infrastructure, they often come with power imbalances. A Tanzanian researcher observed: "In Africa, and most other developing countries, it's like we are doing research, but most of the research is for the interest of your collaborator, not your own interest." The H3ABioNet consortium was cited as an important initiative that promoted equitable funding by supporting African collaborations that built capacity while preserving local autonomy.

Stories from the community

“The truth is that in [country], although we have had governments that have supported science a little more, I don't think it was ever a priority. And with my hand on my heart... I have to be critical because I have lived in developed countries and there has always been a substantial difference in the support and backing for science in [country] compared to other countries.”

This reflection describes a persistent gap between political rhetoric and practical investment in scientific research and infrastructure across many low-resource settings. Several interviewees highlighted that precarious and systemic underinvestment in research at a national level creates a permanent disadvantage for researchers in their countries. Such an underinvestment forces researchers to rely heavily on international collaborations, which, while valuable, can create cycles of dependency and unbalanced relationships.²⁵ This dynamic can also influence research agendas, potentially steering focus away from locally relevant priorities toward topics that align with international interests.

03.

**OPPORTUNITIES AND
NEXT STEPS**

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

This project examined the complex realities faced by researchers in low-resource settings as they engage with the global biodata and bioinformatics ecosystem. Through conversations with stakeholders across Africa, Asia and Latin America, we have gained valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities that exist at the intersection of technical infrastructure, research norms and policy environments.

The research revealed significant variation in experiences across regions. While some countries have developed robust national infrastructure, others struggle with fundamental connectivity issues that limit their participation in the global biodata and bioinformatics landscape. Similarly, the capacity to build and retain a skilled bioinformatics workforce can vary dramatically, influenced by local economic conditions and career pathways. Furthermore, data sharing practices are evolving, with researchers in many low-resource settings pushing back against traditional models that don't adequately address concerns about equitable recognition and ownership. Finally, the funding landscape for biodata research varies significantly between regions, with dramatic differences in national investment priorities, long-term sustainability and political support, creating uneven foundations for research development and collaboration.

At the same time, our assessment of web analytics data has shown that EMBL-EBI resources, training and publishing activities are currently receiving significant uptake from stakeholders in LMICs. This was confirmed by interviewees, who highlighted that the greatest challenge to achieve higher participation in global biodata and bioinformatics resources is not the availability of training and resources but a complex mix of local socio-economic and policy considerations.

Based on these rich contextual insights, we have identified several opportunity areas where EMBL-EBI might support data depositors, users, delivery partners and broader stakeholder communities in low-resource settings. However, it is important to emphasise that these opportunities represent general directions derived from a broad landscape review: they require validation in each specific country or region and cannot be assumed to fit all policy or practice landscapes.

As a result, meaningful progress toward truly global biodata and bioinformatics partnerships will require approaches that respect local contexts, build on existing strengths and create space for collaborative innovation driven by the needs and priorities of local researchers broader communities.

KEY OPPORTUNITIES

TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Develop lightweight versions of tools, including offline versions where possible, to improve usage and access in regions with connectivity challenges.

Develop federated data solutions that enable the hosting of data within national boundaries, mitigating concerns about data ownership and sharing.

Develop tools and processes that make it easier for researchers to contribute to data resources, such as modular workflows to scale up data annotation and curation.

NORMS AND CUSTOMS

Support the wider uptake of robust attribution mechanisms and publication practices that mitigate power imbalances and ensure data generators receive appropriate recognition.

Support "train the trainers" and analogous models to professionalise data resource provision, ensuring skills cascade within countries and reducing dependence on international training.

Support the establishment of clearer expectations on credit and attribution to help address researchers' concerns about recognition and equitable partnership.

POLICIES AND FUNDING

Advocate for strategic national investments in shared infrastructure to create regional nodes of biodata capability, leveraging the success of emerging centres of excellence.

Advocate for novel models to fund biodata resources that can increase long-term resilience, including better coordination between public and private funding streams.

Advocate for the need for equitable partnership frameworks that protect local priorities and ownership when collecting, generating, sharing or hosting biodata resources.

Based on our landscape analysis, we have identified strategic opportunities for EMBL-EBI to support stakeholders in low-resource settings whilst recognising EMBL-EBI's varying degrees of influence across different domains. Naturally, EMBL-EBI maintains strongest control over its own technical infrastructure, which identifies this dimension as key target for direct action. In the case of norms and customs and policies and funding, EMBL-EBI will need to rely on its existing partners and networks to a greater extent, as well as seeking to increase engagement with a broader range of users, data contributors and delivery partners in low-resource settings.

Legend: Opportunities with a global scope

RECOMMENDED NEXT STEPS

Our landscape analysis has identified three practical recommendations to enhance EMBL-EBI's support for biodata and bioinformatics resources in low-resource settings. These provide a framework for pursuing the technical, normative and policy opportunities outlined in the previous page. Importantly, EMBL-EBI should carefully assess the appropriateness of each specific opportunity and recommendation based on regional contexts, existing relationships and local priorities rather than applying a universal approach.

- 1. Develop meaningful engagement with local communities of users, contributors and delivery partners:** In regions where EMBL-EBI's presence is limited, it will be important to establish connections with existing scientific communities and infrastructure providers. EMBL-EBI should not seek to create parallel structures, but identify and engage with established national, regional or broader genomics and bioinformatics projects or networks. These networks already possess local trust, contextual understanding and operational capacity that should not be duplicated.
- 2. Develop a close understanding of local needs, priorities and agendas:** Once communication channels are in place in a given region, EMBL-EBI should endeavour to discover and understand the key needs, priorities and agendas of local stakeholders in the biodata and bioinformatics landscape. This includes identifying opportunities to support local delivery partners in professionalising and maturing their services to participate more effectively in global infrastructure networks through targeted skills cascade approaches. This will serve to maximise the perception of EMBL-EBI as a trusted partner that seeks to genuinely support and enhance local capacity while respecting local leadership, addressing the concerns about ownership and recognition highlighted throughout our analysis.
- 3. Co-develop adapted tools and resources that meet evidenced needs of users, contributors and delivery partners:** After building a clear understanding of priorities and agendas, EMBL-EBI will be well-placed to co-develop with local stakeholders (i) tailored tools and resources; (ii) customised support routes around disciplinary norms and expectations; and (iii) relevant approaches to advocate for changes in existing policies and funding mechanisms. Co-development ensures that any activities pursued by EMBL-EBI address specific rather generalised, global needs and build local capacity for long-term sustainability.

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